

IMPLEMENTATION OF E-MATERIALS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND STUDENTS' DANCE PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the world of education faces a challenging scenario because of the pandemic where everyone is affected. Globalization has an advantage in approaching education and may also be a disadvantage. Schools as entities are doing their best these days to keep up to date with the changes taking place in the world, as well as to adapt to their demands, technology has become mainstream, and the field of education has no intention of falling behind. The study mainly focused on how the implementation of e-materials utilized in teaching and learning physical education dance. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions: (1) What is assessment of the implementation of e-materials in teaching physical education in terms of; software and hardware; role of the teacher, students' readiness; and physical environment, (2) What is the level of the students' performance in dance in terms of: physical skills and technical skills, and; (3) Is there a significant relationship between the e-materials in teaching dance in physical education and students' dance performance? It is a correlational analysis on the implementation of e-materials in physical education and students' dance performance. Using a descriptive-quantitative methodology, a self-administered questionnaire through google form was utilized in the survey of 50 students. They also submitted a performance task inclined in the physical education activity with the used of e-materials and graded by the given rubrics of the teacher. The results revealed that utilization of e-materials in physical education dance are always observed and student's performance is very good with the employment of e-materials. Moreover, there is no significant relationship between the e-materials in teaching dance in physical education and students' dance performance. It encouraged to continue utilizing and employing the effectivity of e-materials in the performance of the students in dancing.

Keywords: a. Physical Education b. e-materials to physical education dance performance c. descriptive-quantitative and self-administered questionnaire through google form d. Philippines